

Fatigue analysis of cruciform welded joints based on E-N curves using numerical methods

Zheng Li^{*,a}, Qiuyue Liu^a, Raphael Erlemann^a, Karsten Geißler^a

^aTechnical University of Berlin, Department of Steel Structure, Berlin Germany
Zheng.li@tu-berlin.de, qiuyue.liu@campus.tu-berlin.de, r.erlemann@tu-berlin.de, ek-stahlbau@tu-berlin.de

ABSTRACT

Welding, a prevalent connection technique in steel structures, has specific requirements in design standards. For each different type of welded joint, fatigue tests are required to determine the corresponding fatigue strength using the nominal stress approach to ensure the structural component's safety. Currently, there is a lack of a comprehensive approaches to elucidate the strength of welded steel structures; the primary strategy remains the establishment of detail categories based on a limited number of tests. The developed approach based on welding simulation will be proposed because the residual stress caused by the welding process has a great influence on the joints fatigue life. Based on the E-N curve of the material-based Wohler curve, the fatigue life of cruciform welded joints is determined by numerical calculations supported by residual stress data derived from welding simulation. To validate this approach, fatigue tests were carried out on specimens with and without welds. Empirical data for cruciform welded joints indicate the effectiveness, accuracy and versatility of the introduced method, suggesting its applicability to different joint types. Consequently, the results demonstrate the accuracy of the numerical method as a potential alternative to extensive experimental investigation.

Keywords: Fatigue, cruciform welded joint, E-N curve, numerical method

1 INTRODUCTION

Fatigue in metallic materials, especially in steel structures, is a complex phenomenon that has challenged engineers and researchers for decades. This process, which results in the gradual deterioration of material properties under repeated loading, is a dominant factor in the failure of steel structures, including bridges, buildings and offshore structures. The inherent danger of fatigue lies in its ability to cause significant damage without visible deformation, leading to sudden and catastrophic failure. Research by the American Society of Civil Engineers in 1982 highlighted that fatigue damage was responsible for 80-90% of structural failures in steel frameworks, emphasising the critical need for effective design and assessment strategies to mitigate this risk. The response to this challenge has been the development of rigorous international standards such as EN 1993 (1) in Europe, BS5400 (2) in the UK, AASHTO (3) in the USA. These standards are mainly based on the nominal stress concept, using S-N curves based on extensive experimental data to categorise fatigue strength and enable engineers to verify the durability of structures under cyclic loading. Despite the widespread adoption of these standards, the application of the concept of nominal stress faces significant challenges, particularly when new structural designs or materials are introduced. The need for extensive fatigue testing in such cases highlights the limitations of existing codes and underlines the complexity of ensuring the safety and reliability of steel structures. This is compounded by the diversity of material properties, fabrication techniques and specific conditions under which structures operate, making the task of applying S-N curves to new steel structures daunting and often impractical.

The fatigue life of steel components is generally considered in two main phases: the initiation of fatigue cracks and their subsequent growth (4). Welding induced residual stresses have a critical influence on both of these phases, adding complexity to the assessment of the fatigue life of welded steel components (5). This area of research has received considerable attention with the aim of understanding the effects of welding on fatigue behaviour and developing methods to accurately predict the fatigue life of welded joints. The search for more effective design strategies against fatigue has led to a wealth of experimental data, which is essential for the engineering verification of structural integrity. However, the limitations of physical testing in terms of time, labour and cost have made numerical analysis an indispensable tool for fatigue assessment.

The engineering community's pursuit of solutions to fatigue issues has led to the development of various computational approaches that go beyond the traditional S-N relationship (6) to include advanced models based on the strain-life (E-N) relationship (7), continuum damage mechanics and fracture mechanics (8). These methods provide nuanced insights into the fatigue process, from improving life assessment techniques to understanding the behaviour of materials under cyclic loading and analysing crack propagation mechanisms. The notch stress concept, based on the S-N curve, accounts for material failure due to local stress concentrations. However, the welding process not only changes the geometry of the structural component, but also induces residual stresses in the specimen due to the high welding temperatures, so that fatigue evaluation based solely on the S-N method is not fully representative of the fatigue behaviour of the welded joints.

The simulation for residual stresses is a critical issue in materials engineering and research due to thermal, mechanical or chemical influences on a structural component. This knowledge is particularly important for welded joints, as residual stresses have a considerable influence on the fatigue behaviour. An effective and economical approach for the determination of residual stresses is the simulation of welding processes. Such simulations allow the calculation and analysis of residual stresses taking into account various welding parameters such as welding speed, current or temperature (9,10). The results of welding simulations can be used to assess the effects of residual stresses on the stress distribution of experimental specimens under cyclic loading. Understanding residual stresses is essential for highly stressed components and helps to predict and improve the fatigue behaviour of materials. Overall, residual stress simulation through welding processes provides a suitable method for determining residual stresses in specimens, contributing to the prediction and improvement of material fatigue performance.

This paper presents a study investigating the feasibility of using numerical analysis to predict the fatigue behaviour of cruciform welded specimens using the E-N curve method. It highlights the advantages of using CNC machines to produce the specimens, which ensure higher weld quality compared to manual techniques. Through experimental investigations and numerical simulations, including consideration of residual stresses and stress concentrations, the research validates the accuracy of E-N curve based numerical methods in predicting fatigue behaviour. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of CNC welding robots in the production of specimens and the potential of numerical simulations to improve the understanding and prediction of fatigue behaviour in welded steel components.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

This study focuses on cruciform welded joints, where the welding parameters are matched to the dimensions specified in the relevant design code. The 12 mm thick steel plates, made from structural steel S355J2, comply with the standard which recommends that the maximum size of the fillet weld should not exceed half the minimum thickness of the plates. Therefore, the fillet weld size is designed to be 4 mm, as shown in Fig. 1. CNC welding robots are used in the manufacturing process, a choice aimed at improving the quality of the welds. This is complemented by grinding of the weld area to improve the weld quality and reduce stress concentrations due to geometric inconsistencies. Comparative investigations are carried out on the specimens of the base material to evaluate their fatigue life under a maximum stress range of $\Delta\sigma = 300$ MPa, with the test frequency set to 4 Hz. The

cross-sectional dimensions were adapted so that the geometric conditions did not have any influence and an acceptable test duration was achieved. The design of the base material specimen was conceived as a dog-bone tensile specimen, featuring a circular cross section of 6 mm diameter. This design incorporated elements such as tangential fillets and continuous radii, a deliberate strategy to direct fractures to specific, predetermined locations during fatigue testing, thereby satisfying the experimental requirements.

Fig. 1 Specimen geometry and dimensions

Despite the high precision of specimens produced by CNC welding robots, variations and imperfections in weld geometry are inevitable due to technical limitations. In this paper, the weld sizes of cruciform welded joints are meticulously measured and evaluated using a developed 3D scanning system (11). The fillet weld profile is accurately captured using a 3D scanner, as shown in Fig. 2. Ensuring that the scanner sensor is vertically aligned with the weld direction on the specimen is critical to the accuracy of these measurements. The acquired data is then processed using Matlab® to generate the necessary point clouds, which provide a three-dimensional visualisation of the weld. Fig. 10 shows the two-dimensional weld cross section, from which the weld thickness is derived from the coordinates of two points on the weld seam edge. This approach not only provides an accurate representation of the actual dimensions of the specimen for experimental purposes, but also facilitates the verification of weld quality against specified standards. Moreover, the accurate weld sizes obtained are used in numerical simulations, contributing to the development of accurate models and thereby improving the accuracy of numerical analysis.

Fig. 2 Scanning specimens and results

The fatigue tests were conducted using the universal testing machine MTS-810 with a maximum force of 250 kN, as shown in Fig. 3. To eliminate the influence of uneven loading on the results, the specimens were fixed centrally. The control system was calibrated to implement the experimental loading parameters, with the stress ratio set at 0.1 and the cyclic loading frequency to be fixed at 4 Hz. All other test parameters were kept constant to ensure comparability of results. The test was performed until complete failure of the specimen, with stress data meticulously recorded throughout the test for further analysis.

Fig. 3 Test set-up with direct current potential drop measurements for crack detection

The direct current (DC) potential method was employed throughout the tests to accurately determine the onset of fatigue crack initiation, excluding the fatigue crack propagation phase. This technique involves the use of a two-layer sensor: an insulating layer adhered directly to the surface of the specimen, followed by a conductive layer. The presence of cracks in the steel structure specimen reduces the conductivity of the conductive layer, disrupting its electric field and causing significant changes in the potential distribution. By monitoring fluctuations in the output voltage of the conductive layer, the presence of structural cracks and their lengths can be accurately detected and measured. Figure 3 shows the configuration of the measurement system.

Fig. 4 Results of potentiometric crack monitoring

The application of the DC potential method to the fatigue testing of weld specimens allows the derivation of mean voltage values for the four welds investigated, as shown in Fig. 4, which clearly shows the variation in voltage of the welds under cyclic loading. In particular, welds 1 and 4 show a significant increase in voltage at the onset of cracking. The progression of the mean voltage values and the number of cycles during the cracking process for welds 1 and 4 is shown in detail in the right half of Fig. 4. A comparative analysis of the voltage values of all four welds throughout the cracking process indicates that cracking began at approximately 141,000 to 158,000 cycles and culminated in the failure of the specimen. The cracking phase spanned approximately 11% of the total number of

cycles, which is significantly higher than the typical 5% observed in total fatigue cycles. These results confirm the suitability of the potentiometric method for effectively monitoring cracking in welds.

3 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS

It is widely recognised that fatigue of welded joints is closely related to stress or strain concentration. Stress concentrations in welded components are primarily determined by two factors: the geometry of the component and the residual stresses produced by welding. The influence of geometry on these stress concentrations can be captured by modelling specific joint details. However, the residual stresses require prior experimental measurement or welding simulation and subsequent cyclic loading simulation to be included in the analysis. In this paper, a 3D welding simulation is used to determine the residual stresses generated by the welding process. The stress-strain distribution of the model containing the welding residual stresses during a cycle is then calculated. Finally, based on the results obtained, the number of cyclic loads during fatigue initiation is analysed using the E-N curve method.

3.1 Influence of residual stress on stress concentration

This investigation uses sequentially coupled welding simulation, whereby a heat transfer analysis is performed first to inform a subsequent thermomechanical analysis. The temperature field analysis considers welding speed, current and voltage to simulate heat distribution and understand the thermal behaviour of the material during welding. The results guide the thermal stress analysis, which uses the coefficient of thermal expansion to calculate thermal stresses and assess material suitability. Weld dimensions are accurately defined using scan data, improving simulation accuracy by providing a detailed representation of welds. Welding parameters, such as current and voltage, are determined by the size of the weld toe, with the relationship documented in the literature. The numerical model uses 1 mm as the smallest unit, allowing detailed consideration of welds for more accurate results. A detailed description of the welding simulation and analysis can be found in references (12).

Fig. 5 shows the stress distribution under cyclic loading, taking into account residual stresses. The left plot shows the correlation between the duration of the cyclic loading and the nominal stress, where the cyclic loading was realised with a stress range $\Delta\sigma$ of 200 MPa and a stress ratio R of 0.1. The diagram on the right shows the stress distribution during one loading cycle. It is evident that very high stresses occur in the surrounding area of the weld, particularly when residual stresses are taken into account. This is due to the additional tensile stress supplementary to the residual stresses, highlighting the significant influence of residual stresses on the stress distribution.

Fig. 5 Stress distribution under cyclic loading

Using a Python script, the values of stress components for each integration point can be extracted from the ODB file in Abaqus®. Fig. 5 shows the stress distribution at maximum and minimum cyclic loading. The difference between the stress distributions at maximum and minimum loading can be defined as the $\Delta\sigma$ distribution. Due to symmetry, it is possible to analyse the $\Delta\sigma$ distribution around

a weld seam, as illustrated in the orange highlighted area of the figure. The analysis of $\Delta\sigma$ distributions at weld joints, both with and without consideration of welding residual stresses, reveals that the nominal stress near the weld seam is 200 MPa. It is evident that a stress concentration occurs in the area of the weld toe. This stress concentration becomes even more pronounced when the residual stresses of welding distortion is taken into account. The max. $\Delta\sigma$ -values are 265 MPa and 245 MPa. To obtain more comprehensive conclusions, numerous numerical simulations were performed with varying parameters. These models were used to analyse the influence of residual stresses generated during the welding process on the stress concentration. The maximum residual stress value at the weld relative to the defined nominal stress is referred to as the stress concentration factor. Fig. 6 illustrates the relationship between this stress amplification factor and the stress range. The red line in the graph represents the scenario where residual stresses are considered, while the black line represents the condition without residual stresses. It can be seen that the value of the red line, i.e. with residual stresses considered, is consistently higher than that of the black line. It can be estimated that approximately 30-40% of the stress concentration is due to residual stresses. Furthermore, the relationship between the stress amplification factor and the stress range is of significant importance. Without considering residual stresses, there is an almost linear and constantly stable relationship between these two quantities. When the residual stresses are included in the analysis, a non-linear relationship between the stress amplification factor and the stress range is evident. It is observed that the stress amplification factor decreases continuously as the stress range increases. This decreasing trend becomes more pronounced as the stress range increases, which is highlighted by the blue shaded area in the figure. The reason for this non-linear relationship could be that the weld residual stresses are close to or already at the yield point of the material. The additional stress of cyclic loading on the residual stresses causes parts of the material to transition into the plastic region. This non-linear transition undoubtedly poses a significant challenge to the integrity of welded steel components. Therefore, a precise analysis of the residual stress distribution is crucial for assessing stress concentration and estimating the fatigue life.

Fig. 6 Relationship between stress concentration factor and stress range

3.2 Fatigue analysis based on E-N curve

The traditional S-N curve is unable to accurately describe the fatigue behaviour of welded specimens because the material in the vicinity of the weld enters a plastic state due to the combined effect of cyclic loading and residual stress. To overcome this limitation, this study incorporates stress and strain data from integration points across all elements to perform an accurate fatigue life analysis based on the E-N curves (13,14). Stress-strain result files, including stress state from a loading cycle and residual stress, are input into the program FE-Safe®. The parameters of the E-N curve are then iteratively adjusted to match the true fatigue behaviour of the base material specimen. For the purposes of this numerical model, cracks greater than 5 mm in length are considered to be the onset

of fatigue cracking. Numerical simulations of cruciform welded specimens, using identical fatigue analysis parameter settings, were carried out to validate the effectiveness of the E-N curve method for both welded and non-welded components.

The E-N curve describes the relationship between the fatigue life of a material and its strains, established by analysing strain data along with the corresponding number of cycles to failure, as described in equation (1).

$$\frac{\Delta\varepsilon}{2} = \frac{\sigma'_f}{E} (2N_f)^b + \varepsilon'_f (2N_f)^c \quad (1)$$

where b and c signify the fatigue strength exponent (Basquin's exponent) and the fatigue ductility exponent (the Coffin-Manson exponent), respectively. Additionally, σ'_f and ε'_f denote the fatigue strength coefficient and the fatigue ductility coefficient, with the latter representing the plastic strain amplitude when $2N_f$ equals 1. According to the results of tensile tests and parametric studies, in this paper, the Young's modulus is defined as 197 GPa, and the four parameters describing the E-N curve are defined as -0.165, -0.502, 1521 and -0.402 respectively.

In Fig. 7 the four black dots represent the results of the fatigue tests carried out on the base material specimen. The considerable variation observed in these results is due to the use of a fatigue testing machine with a maximum capacity of 250 kN, whereas the maximum tensile load required for the base material specimen is just over 11 kN. Nevertheless, the congruence between the fitted curves derived from the simulation results and those from the experimental results is remarkable, with a difference in m values of less than 10%.

Fig. 7 Comparison of fatigue curves from numerical simulation and experimental data for base material specimens

The S-N curves depicted in Fig. 8 illustrate the effectiveness of the E-N curve method, together with the parameters chosen, in accurately characterising the fatigue behaviour of cruciform welded specimens. The m value obtained from the experiment is equal to 2.88, but the value obtained by numerical methods of 3.27 is slightly higher, except that the results for the base material specimen are opposite.

It is notable that the simulation outcomes for material samples, utilizing identical parameters and the E-N curve, align closely with the experimental fatigue test data. This alignment indicates the E-N curve method's capability to accurately depict the fatigue behaviour of both, welded and base metal samples, irrespective of notch conditions. The findings suggest that the E-N curve method effectively addresses the shortcomings of previous methodologies, highlighting its potential as a valuable approach in fatigue analysis research. Anticipated is a significant enhancement in the evaluation of fatigue life through numerical analyses grounded in the E-N curve approach.

Fig. 8 Comparison of fatigue curves from numerical simulation and experimental data for weld joints

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper introduces an innovative approach for fatigue analysis of welded components using the E-N curve method, delineating its superiority over conventional S-N curve techniques, particularly in capturing the plastic effects inherent in welding processes. The accuracy of this approach is underlined by the precision of CNC-controlled welded specimens, which are further validated through extensive 3D scanning to ensure the compliance of weld dimensions. Additionally, the application of potentiometric monitoring has provided valuable insights into crack initiation and propagation mechanisms, enriching the understanding of fatigue behaviour in welded structures.

The appropriate E-N curve parameters are obtained through parametric research, so that the simulated fatigue life can be closely linked to the fatigue test results of the base material specimen, and then the cruciform welded joints can be predicted and analysed. This refined analysis highlights the critical role of residual stresses and stress concentrations in the fatigue performance of welds and demonstrates the ability of the E-N curve method to accurately model these factors.

The outcome of this research highlights the potential of the E-N curve approach to significantly advance the fatigue analysis of welded structural components. Future work will aim to further improve these analysis techniques, extend their applicability, and validate their effectiveness over a wider range of welding conditions.

REFERENCES

1. **European Committee for Standardization (CEN).** Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures –Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings; German version EN 1993-1-1:2005 + AC:2009.
2. **British Standards Institution (BSI).** BS 5400. Steel, concrete and composite bridges - part 10: Code of practice for fatigue. London: BSI, 1980.
3. **American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO).** LRFD Bridge design specifications, 3rd edition. Washington, DC: AASHTO, 2010
4. **Röscher S., Knobloch M.** Towards a prognosis of fatigue life using a Two-Stage-Model. Steel Construction, 2019, 12 (3), pp. 198-208.

5. **Xin H., Veljkovic M.**, Residual stress effects on fatigue crack growth rate of mild steel S355 exposed to air and seawater environments *Mater Des*, 193 (2020), Article 108732, 10.1016/j.matdes.2020.108732.
6. **Erlemann, R., Kraus, J., Geißler, K.** Fatigue strength of the joint of steel cantilevers in composite bridges. 10. Eurosteel Konferenz in Amsterdam, ce-papers (9/2023), Band 6, No. 3-4.
7. **Hassanifard S., Hashemi S.M.** On the strain-life fatigue parameters of additive manufactured plastic materials through fused filament fabrication process *Addit Manuf*, 32 (2020), Article 100973, 10.1016/j.addma.2019.100973.
8. **Xin H.** Recent progress in computational predictions on fatigue and fracture resistance of steel connection joints. 10. Eurosteel Konferenz in Amsterdam, ce-papers (9/2023), Band 6, No. 3-4.
9. **Li Z., Xu S.Y., Geißler K., Wang J., Pasternak H.** Developed numerical Analysis of Residual Stress caused by Welding and Cutting in Steel Structures, *Proceedings in civil engineering: Eurosteel Amsterdam 2023*, September 2023, ce/papers 6(3-4):1507-1512.
10. **Launert B., Li Z., Pasternak H.** Development of a new method for the direct numerical consideration of welding effects in the component design of welded plate girders. In: *Advances in Engineering Materials, Structures and Systems: Innovations, Mechanics and Applications*, Hrsg. Alphose Zingoni, 2019, S. 1143-1147.
11. **Li Z., Zhang Q.L, Shi F., Wang J., Pasternak H.** Geometric Properties of Steel Components with Stability and Fatigue Risks Using 3D-Laser-Scanning. January 2024 *Buildings* 2024 (14) (168):1-21.
12. **Launert B.** Untersuchungen an geschweißten I-Trägern aus normal- und hochfestem Baustahl: Beitrag zur Erweiterung der Tragfähigkeitsnachweise durch Einsatz der Schweißsimulation (Dissertation). 2019. Schriftenreihe Stahlbau, BTU Cottbus Senftenberg.
13. **Morrow J.** *Fatigue Design Handbook*. Society of Automotive Engineers, 1968, Sec 3.2, pp. 21-29.
14. **Smith K. N., Watson P., Topper T. H.** A Stress-Strain Function for the Fatigue of metals. *J Mater*, Vol 5, No 4, 1970, pp. 767-778.